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Abstract

Carbon capture is one of the recently raised technologies to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions. Adsorption is an energy-efficient carbon capture process, and the adsorbent material plays a major role in determining its effectiveness. Metal Organic Framework adsorbent materials (MOFs) are a new class of microporous material with exceptionally high surface area, porous volume and adsorption characteristics. This project is to carry out comprehensive literature reviews of over 30 different MOFs for separation and capturing of CO₂ from flue gases using top high level research publication and journal like science direct, Elsevier, research gate, ACS, MDPI, etc. The review will compare the performance of various MOFs materials for the separation, then identify high performing candidates which will be tested for their effectiveness. Results showed that the top candidates tested and simulated are Mg- MOF -74, HKUST -1, ZIF- 8 UIO-66, MIL-101, MOF-303 with average porosity void of 0.7, CO₂ uptake of 7.5, 6.3, 5.3, 4.2, 5.3, 6.4, 6.5, mmol/g respectively heat rate of q_{max} of 430KKJ/g. Using Langmuir-isotherm model equation embedded in MATLAB code implementation to generate plots of performance metrics in relation to numerous parameters. The gas flow passing through the packed bed is CO₂ diatomic gas, which enters at a speed of from 1 to 4 m/s and the outlet is defined as atmospheric pressure (zero Pascal gauge pressure). The packed bed area is a porous medium with an inertial resistance of 45 (1/m) and a viscous resistance of $3e9$ (1/m²). The CFD used pressure-based solver method, steady flow, with gravity effect ignored. K-epsilon viscous adoption was used in this testing. The Viscous model used is K-epsilon standard for the CO₂ flow inward and outward bound of porous packed bed. This study investigates the CO₂ adsorption performance of 10 different high-performing metal-organic frameworks in relation to packed bed reactor wall heating transfer as well using MATLAB implementation.

Keywords: MOFs, CO₂ capture, packed-bed, adsorption, desorption heat wall transfer, Matlab, ANSYS Fluent, K-epsilon viscous flow, turbulent kinetics flow, heat wall transfer.

1.

Introduction

Fossil fuels remain a key and dominant source in global electricity production, supplying nearly two-thirds of the world's power despite the increasing use of renewable energy alternatives. Since

2000, reliance on fossil fuels for electricity has risen by about 70%, largely due to growing driven energy demand. Coal and natural gas continue to serve as main fuels for electricity generation, making up to around 38% and 20% respectively. The surge in global CO₂ emissions in recent years is primary linked to rising energy use. Carbon emissions from industrial activities continue to rise each year, with the power generation sector being the largest contributor, accounting for nearly 40% of global carbon output. In 2019, CO₂ emissions reached almost 13.6 gigatons, close to the record level seen in 2018, despite efforts to curb them [1].

The Paris Agreement, established at COP 21, represents a global initiative to tackle climate change and promote a low-carbon, sustainable future. Its central objective to restrict global temperatures increase to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels, with a further target of limiting the rise to 1.5°C. The agreement also emphasizes the need to align financial systems with low-carbon development and strengthen resilience against climate impacts. Meeting these goals requires significant reductions in emissions across power generation, transportation, industrial, and agricultural sectors [2]. Carbon emissions stem from both concentrated sources, like power plants and industrial sites, as well as more dispersed sources, though carbon capture at concentrated point is more practical and cost effective [2]. Advances in natural gas exploration and extraction have increased its role as a key energy resource, with methane (CH₄) gaining prominence due to availability. However, biogas generated through processes like anaerobic digestion can contain up to 60% CO₂ [4], which harms the environment and lowers the fuel efficiency by reducing heating value [5]. Due to this, it is crucial to separate CO₂ from methane prior to transporting or utilizing natural gas. A plethora of technologies have been developed to capture and reduce CO₂ emissions, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Technologies used for carbon dioxide capture [3].

Cryogenic separation is widely used in industry to process CO₂ gas streams that contain high concentrations—typically above 90%. This method separates CO₂ by cooling the gas mixture to very low temperatures, causing CO₂ to condense into liquid or solid form based on the differing boiling points of the mixture’s components, while other gases remain gaseous [6]. Despite its effectiveness, cryogenic separation demands substantial energy for refrigeration and is not efficient for gas streams with low CO₂ concentrations. Additionally, water and other impurities such as NO_x and SO_x must be removed prior to cooling to avoid blockages and maintain operational efficiency [7].

Membrane separation achieves gas separation by permitting one gas component to permeate through the membrane more rapidly than others. For effective separation, the membrane must exhibit high permeability to allow CO₂ to pass through easily, high selectivity to preferentially separate CO₂ molecules from other gases, and strong chemical and physical stability to withstand demanding industrial environments. Meeting all these criteria is challenging, particularly since polymeric membranes, which are commonly used, often face limitations in stability and overall performance [8].

Chemical absorption is one of the most applied methods for CO₂ capture, where CO₂ reacts chemically to form stable compounds that are later transported to a regeneration column. In this stage, heat is applied to break the chemical bonds, releasing pure CO₂ gas. This approach is particularly effective under low CO₂ concentrations or pressures conditions and usually requires gas-liquid contact withing separation equipment, where the gas and liquid flow counter-currently through a vertical column [7].

A widely used solvent in this process is Mono-ethanolamine (MEA), an amine-based compound. Despite its effectiveness, this method has several limitations. It demands high energy demand for solvent regeneration, typically requiring 3–5 MJ of heat per kilogram of CO₂, which raises operational costs and reduces overall efficiency [10]. Moreover, an IEA report noted that about 0.0032 tons of MEA are released into the atmosphere for every ton of CO₂ captured, leading to notable solvent losses over time [11].

An alternative method for gas separation is adsorption, in which gas molecules attach to the solid surface of a solid material (adsorbent) that has a large surface area relative to its volume [12]. Compared to absorption, adsorption is more energy efficient at high temperatures and requires less energy for regeneration [13]. The type of adsorbent material plays a major role in determining how effectively CO₂ can be separated.

Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) have drawn significant interest as potential materials for CO₂ capture. due to their high porosity, chemical tunability, and strong interactions with CO₂ molecules, especially at low pressures conditions [14]. A plethora of enhancements have been made to improve and synthesize the chemical and physical characteristics of MOFs through precise design, synthesis, and post-synthetic modifications to achieve their respective optimum performance to CO₂ selectivity and uptake. Unlike traditional adsorbents such as zeolites and activated carbons, which primarily rely on weak physisorption, MOFs exhibit superior CO₂ uptake owing to their exceptionally large surface areas and customizable properties. These features enable MOFs to selectively adsorb CO₂ over other gases like N₂, CH₄, and H₂O, making them highly promising for carbon capture applications [15]. Several adsorption-based CO₂ separation techniques exist, including Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA), Temperature Swing Adsorption (TSA), Vacuum Swing Adsorption (VSA), as well as hybrid methods such as Pressure and Temperature Swing Adsorption (PTSA) and Vacuum Pressure and Temperature Swing Adsorption (VTSA), as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) is a cyclic technique used to separate and capture CO₂ from flue gas by leveraging on the variable adsorption capacities of adsorbents under varying pressures. During the adsorption process, a gas stream (flue gas) containing CO₂ is passed through a packed-bed column at high pressure [16], where CO₂ molecules preferentially adhere to the adsorbent surface due to their stronger affinity compared to gases like nitrogen or hydrogen. When the adsorbent reaches saturation, the pressure is lowered during the desorption phase, causing the CO₂ to be released and collected, while regenerating the adsorbent for reuse in future cycles [17].

This method is energy-efficient since regeneration is driven by pressure reduction instead of heat application, as seen in solvent-based chemical absorption methods. Common solid adsorbents for PSA include zeolites, activated carbon, and metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), all of which can be reused multiple times, lowering operational expenses. These materials also provide high selectivity and CO₂ capacity under certain conditions, making PSA well-suited for applications like natural gas processing, hydrogen purification, and CO₂ capture [18].

However, traditional adsorbents such as zeolites have limited selectivity and can suffer from competitive adsorption by impurities like water. Frequent pressure cycling may also degrade these materials. MOFs have demonstrated superior CO₂ adsorption performance compared to conventional adsorbents like zeolites and activated carbons [19]. They exhibit higher CO₂ uptake and require lower regeneration temperatures (around 100°C), enhancing efficiency in CO₂ capture processes. Additionally, some MOFs perform better under humid conditions, such as in flue gases from coal power plants [21].

The ability to tailor MOF pore size, shape, and functional groups further optimizes their gas separation and CO₂ capture capabilities, offering advantages over traditional adsorbents [22].

Temperature Swing Adsorption (TSA) can be defined as a method for regenerating adsorbents by raising their temperature. TSA operations are implemented in two ways: the direct mode, where a hot gas stream such as steam or CO₂ directly contacts the adsorbent particles to facilitate regeneration, and the indirect mode, where heat is supplied via a packed-bed reactor known to be heat exchanger without direct interaction between the hot gas and the adsorbent. The regeneration process involves three heat components: sensible heat to raise the adsorbent to the required regeneration temperature, reaction heat to drive the endothermic desorption reactions, and latent heat to vaporize water present in the adsorbent [23]. Vacuum Swing Adsorption (VSA) works by varying pressure feed of gas plugged into the reactor to capture CO₂, making it especially suitable for post-combustion CO₂ capture. VSA is generally more cost-effective and is commonly used in fixed-bed reactors packed with adsorbents like zeolites and activated carbon. This allows for short cycle times but requires a reduced pressure drop across the bed during adsorption, favoring the use of structured advanced fixed beds. Achieving high CO₂ capture rates with VSA demands deep vacuum levels, making it ideal for industrial flue gases with high CO₂ partial pressure. Experimental results indicate that VSA can reach CO₂ purity levels around 99%, although recovery rates tend to be lower, approximately 85% [24]. To improve recovery, techniques such as recycling CO₂ (heavy reflux or high-pressure rinse) have been suggested in this scenario, and its

implementation has been effective, increasing recovery to about 98.7% with a purity close to 98.7% [25]. The various carbon capture adsorption methods are illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Adsorption / regeneration modes: TSA, temperature swing adsorption; VSA, vacuum swing adsorption; PSA, Pressure swing adsorption VTSA /PTSA, combine with temperature swing [4].

Fig 3.1 Metric performance of mofs CO₂ uptake in mmol/g versus range of MOFs index reviewed. [5]

Fig 3.2 Metric performance of mofs CO₂ surface area in m²/g versus range of MOFs index reviewed [5]

Fig 3.3 Metric performance of MOFs pore volume in cm³/g versus range of MOFs index reviewed [5]

Fig 3.4 Metric performance of mofs isotherm temperature (K) versus range of MOFs index reviewed [5]

Fig 3.5 Metric performance of MOFs pressure in bar versus range of MOFs index reviewed [5]

Fig 3.6 Metric performance of MOFs number of data points versus range of MOFs index reviewed [5]

MOFs Industrial application and challenges

Metal-organic frameworks MOFs show great promise for industrial CO₂ capture but face challenges in scalable, cost-effective synthesis with consistent quality. High space-time yields and environmentally friendly methods are key for industrial viability. Stability under humid conditions and thermal regeneration are critical for durability in direct air capture (DAC) applications. Effective (MOFs) packing into pellets or monoliths is essential for practical use but may affect adsorption performance and mechanical strength. Ongoing optimization is required to balance CO₂ capture efficiency, material stability, and operational feasibility [5].

Metal-Organic Frameworks MOFs are highly promising nanomaterials for CO₂ capture due to their large size of surface area, tunable pore sizes, and abundant adsorption sites such as open metal and Lewis's acid sites. Metal-Organic Frameworks MOFs are promising in CO₂ capture and uptake, such as MOF-74, MOF-210 have demonstrated strong CO₂ uptake and capacities, showing enhanced adsorption due to the presence of unsaturated centers. However, challenges such as poor CO₂ selectivity in humid or acidic environments and conditions instability under such conditions limit their performance. Strategies like pore size manipulation, post-synthetic modifications, and bimetallic MOFs can improve CO₂ storage performance, but often raise production costs. Future research is currently focusing on low-cost, economically ecofriendly synthesis methods and MOFs designs that ensure stability and efficiency for practical carbon capture and storage CCS applications

2. Modeling Methodology using MATLAB

MATLAB was solely used for modeling in this study. The adsorbent bed setup consists of a steel pipe measuring 2 m in length filled with adsorbent powder embedded inside the porous bed, CO₂ gas introduced at the inlet under a pressure of 0-10bars, with ambient conditions assumed for the surroundings. The simulation captures heat and mass transfer phenomena, including conduction and convection, between the pipe interior, pipe wall, and environment. The model incorporates

both standard and customized modules to represent diffusion, convection, and conduction processes. The governing equations for these heat and mass transfer mechanisms are detailed below.

Figure 3. Adsorbent bed setup consists of adsorbent material filled inside steel pipe with an inlet of gas mixture and heat of adsorption generated [3].

Property	Cylinder wall
Material type	Stainless steel-316
Density (kg/m ³)	7941
Thermal conductivity (W/m·K)	15.14
Heat capacity (J/kg·K)	$358.98 T + 0.487394 T^2 - 2.65708 \times 10^{-7} T^3$

Figure 3 Thermal properties of the adsorbent material [26].

2.1 Mass Balance Equations

The individual gas species entering the pipe are described by the following equations:

$$\frac{\partial c_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(uc_i)}{\partial z} + \rho_s \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial t} - \epsilon D \frac{\partial^2 c_i}{\partial z^2} = 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, N$$

The overall mass balance for the gas mixture is given by:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(uc)}{\partial z} + \rho_s \sum_i \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial t} = 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, N$$

In these expressions, c and q denote the fluid-phase concentration and adsorbed amount per species i , both in moles per unit mass. Here, u is the superficial gas velocity, ϵ -epsilon is the bed porosity, and ρ_s is the bulk density of the packed bed. The parameter D represents the axial dispersion coefficient, it is time, and z is the axial coordinate along the column. The molar fraction of gas species is y , while c is the molar concentration of the gas mixture, and N is the total number of gas components.

The total porosity ϵ -epsilon is defined as the ratio of total pore volume—including both intergranular and intragranular pores—to the total volume occupied by the material inside the tube [43], and can also be expressed in terms of bulk density ρ_s and skeletal density ρ_m as:

$$\epsilon = 1 - \frac{\rho_s}{\rho_m}$$

2.2 Energy Balance Equation

The energy conservation in the system is governed by:

$$C_g \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_s C_s \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_s C_{ads} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \epsilon \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + u C_g \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} - \sum_i (-\Delta H_i) \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial t} + h_{in} A_{in} (T - T_w) - \epsilon K \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} = 0$$

Where C_g , C_s , and C_{ads} are the heat capacities of the gas phase, solid phase, and adsorbed phase, respectively. ΔH_i is the heat of adsorption for each gas species, ϵ -epsilon is the total porosity, T and p represent temperature and pressure in the column, T_w is the wall temperature, h_{in} is the heat transfer coefficient between the column interior and wall, A_{in} is the internal surface area, and K denotes the axial thermal conductivity.

Heat exchange between the column wall and the environment is described by:

$$C_w A \frac{\partial T_w}{\partial t} = 2\pi R_{in} h_{in} (T - T_w) - 2\pi R_{out} h_{out} (T_w - T_{env})$$

Where C_w is the heat capacity of the wall, A is its cross-sectional area, R_{in} and R_{out} are the inner and outer radii of the column wall, h_{out} is the heat transfer coefficient to the environment, and T_{env} is the ambient temperature.

2.3 Momentum Equation

The momentum balance is given by Darcy's law:

$$u = -\frac{\kappa}{\mu} \nabla p$$

Where ∇p is the pressure gradient, u is the gas velocity, κ is the permeability of the porous medium, μ is the constant dynamic viscosity, and d is the particle diameter.

2.4 Adsorption Isotherm and Kinetic Equations

The adsorption kinetics are modeled using the Linear Driving Force (LDF) approach, where the adsorbed amount q changes over time as:

$$\frac{dq_i}{dt} = k_i (q_i^* - q_i), \quad i = 1, \dots, N$$

The equilibrium adsorbed amount q_i^* is estimated by the Langmuir isotherm:

$$q_i^* = q_{sat} \frac{K_i p_i}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^N K_j p_j}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N$$

Where the Langmuir constants q_{sat} and K_i vary with temperature as:

$$q_{sat} = a_i \exp\left(-\frac{E_{a,i}}{RT}\right), \quad K_i = b_i \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H_i}{RT}\right), \quad i = 1, \dots, N$$

The gas mixture behavior is simplified using the ideal gas law to reduce model complexity.

2.5 Model Parameters and Boundary Conditions

An adiabatic boundary condition is applied for simplicity:

- At the inlet ($z = 0, t > 0$): velocity $u(0, t) = u_{in}$; temperature $T(0, t) = T_{in} = 298.15 \text{ K}$; molar fraction $y_i(0, t) = y_{i,in}, i = 1, \dots, N$.
- At the outlet ($z = 1.2 \text{ m}, t > 0$): gradients of velocity, temperature, and concentration are zero.
- Initially ($0 \leq z \leq \text{length}, t = 0$): $y_i(z, 0) = 0$ for all gases except the initial gas; temperature $T(z, 0) = T_{in}$.

Tables 2 and 3 summarize the key geometric, heat transfer parameters, and Langmuir constants for activated carbon used for model validation. The adsorption data were sourced from [33].

DESIGN & SIMULATION TESTING

Model- Geometry Parameters Used in the CFD simulation

Length	2000mm (2m)	Stainless steel 316
Diameter	400mm (0.4m)	Stainless steel 316
Aspect ratio	L/D = 5.00	
Volume	251,327,412 mm ³ = 251 liters	
Bed porosity	0.7 (70%)	MOFs materials

Fig 4.1 Design parameters for the porous packed bed

SolidWorks was used to design the model with length of packed porous bed of 2000mm and diameter of 400mm and flange of 460 mm, also the tube channel was designed in the SolidWorks, the packed porous bed as depicted represent average MOFs especially the metal open sites known for exothermic adsorption of co2 and as we know that this require optimization for the wall of the system in other for the process to be sustainable heat wall transfer management needed to be tested and doing this K-epsilon CFD fluent via ANSYS was adopted to simulate its dynamics and in so doing the SolidWorks model was transfer into ANSYS to me meshed, after meshing then set-up was done by introducing all necessary equation of porosity and

Fig 5.1 Showing SolidWorks design of the model packed bed porous zone meant for simulation domain CFD

Fig 5.2 Showing full SolidWorks set-up rig before plugged in into ANSYS fluent workspace after bed plug in

	model	Equation
Viscous model	Standard	K-epsilon
Cell zone conditions	Porous zone	On
	Inertial resistance	45 (1/m)
	Viscous resistance	3e9 (1/m)
Laminar zone		On
Boundary conditions	Inlet velocity= 4 m/s	Outlet pressure = 0 pascal
Walls	Stationary wall	
Spatial discretization	Pressure	Second -order
Momentum	Turbulent kinetic energy Turbulent dissipation rate	Second –order Second order upwind
Initialization method	Hybrid Implementation	Hybrid Implementation

Figure 5.3 Shows the boundaries conditions implemented in the testing's CFD.

Figure 5.4 Showing the cross-sectional view of the reactor and porous packed bed length

Figure 5.5 Showing when the whole set up test rig is implemented in the domain of ANSYS ready to be meshed for CFD analysis

Meshing of the model

Figure 5.7 Showing model meshed, ready to set up boundary conditions of the flow conditions from the inlet to the outlet.

Figures 5.8 Showing how the porous section was assigned to and how the flow rate and velocity of CO2 was assigned to model

Figure 5.9 Showing how the full setup was configured and finally ready for result test run

ANSYS Results and Discussion

Figure 6.0 Showing how the log space of test results of iteration of K-epsilon was generated

Figure 7.2 Show the static wall temperature and the static pressure contour

Figure 7.3 Show the static turbulent kinetic contour

Iteration	k	epsilon
1	37.134	41757
2	0.084032	0.34381
3	0.057987	0.22634
4	0.039756	0.12968
5	0.028468	0.09241
6	0.020772	0.06673
7	0.016191	0.05414
8	0.013463	0.04605
9	0.011465	0.04012
10	0.010053	0.03527
11	0.009068	0.03119
12	0.008362	0.02763
13	0.007836	0.02448
14	0.007418	0.02164
15	0.007051	0.01907
16	0.0067	0.01677
17	0.00635	0.01469
18	0.006	0.01282
19	0.00565	0.01113
20	0.0053	0.0096

Figure 7.4 Show the main results depicting iteration log of K-epsilon both turbulent kinetic and epsilon formations

Figure 8.1 Show convergence plot of turbulent kinetic energy and turbulent dissipation rate K-epsilon variable of the CO2 flow through the packed bed

Results and Discussion

The plot illustrates the convergence behavior of the CO2 flow turbulence variables k (turbulent kinetic energy) and ϵ (turbulent dissipation rate) over 20 solver iterations. Initially, both variables show extremely high values – particularly epsilon, which starts at around 41757- indicative of the solvers initial guess and the flow field initialization phase. As the iteration progresses, both kinetic and epsilon sharply decrease and begin to stabilize, demonstrating the numerical solvers' progress toward a physically realistic and stable turbulence solution. As shown in table (figure 7.1, 7.9, 8.1) There are clear indications that depict high pressure drops occurring in the porous area of the packed bed. The amount of pressure drop is directly related to the magnitude of the defined viscous and inertial resistance. To overcome this high-pressure drop, there is a need for the provision of pressure required to cross this barrier porosity in the pathway of CO2 gas even before the gas enters the packed bed area using a pressure-boosting element such as a compressor booster. In as much as MOFs membranes packed in the bed are not affected by degradation so far, and its open metal sites are not affected by corrosion or degradation of linkers. The logarithmic scale used on both y-axes is crucial to capture the wide dynamic range and rapid decay of these turbulence parameters, reflecting the solvers effective damping of transient numerical artifacts. By iteration 10, both kinetic and epsilon approach asymptotic values, indicating that the turbulence model has reached near-converged states, consistent with fully developed turbulent flow characteristics. As shown in table (figure 7.1a to 8.1) The decreasing trend in kinetic k suggests the kinetic energy of turbulent eddies is diminishing and stabilizing, which is expected as the flow approaches steady-state turbulence conditions. Similarly, the reduction and eventual plateau in epsilon ϵ signifies the dissipation rate of turbulence energy balancing the production rate, a hallmark of turbulence equilibrium in the kinetic k – epsilon ϵ model framework. This convergence pattern confirms the robustness and stability of the chosen turbulence model and numerical scheme within ANSYS Fluent or CFX. Moreover, smooth decay without oscillation or divergence implies adequate mesh quality, appropriate time step or relaxation factors, and properly defined boundary conditions.

Overall, the result provides confidence in the accuracy of and reliability of the turbulence simulation, ensuring that subsequent post-processing, such as velocity profile or wall shear stress analysis will be based on a converged physically consistent flow solution.

MATLAB Result and Discussion

```

%>> clear; clc; close all;

%% Reactor Geometry and Conditions
L = 2.0; % Length [m]
d_tube = 0.025; % Tube diameter [m]
d_shell = 0.1; % Shell diameter [m]
A_shell = pi * d_shell^2 * L; % Max exchange area [m^2]

% Heat transfer parameters
U = 150; % Overall heat transfer coefficient [kW/m^2.K]
T_inlet = 323; % Inlet gas temperature [K]
T_wall = 298; % Wall temperature [K]
Cp_gas = 1.1; % Specific heat capacity [kJ/kg.K]
mass_flow = 0.01; % Gas mass flow rate [kg/s]

% Pressure range [bar]
P = 1:10;

%% MOF Database (Name, q_max [mmol/g], b [1/bar], cho_bulk [kg/m^3])
MOFs = [
'MOF-74', 20, 0.8, 1300;
'MOF-5', 11.4, 1.1, 1300;
'ZIF-8', 0.4, 0.9, 1000;
'UiO-66', 2.0, 0.7, 1300;
'MIL-101', 8.0, 1.8, 700;
'MOF-303', 15.0, 1.5, 800;
];

% Colors = lines(size(MOFs,1));
% Plot 1: Langmuir Isotherm (CO2 Uptake in mmol/g)
figure(1); hold on;
for i = 1:size(MOFs,1)
    name = MOFs(i,1);
    q_max = MOFs(i,2);
    b = MOFs(i,3);
    uptake = q_max * b * P ./ (1 + b * P); % mmol/g
    plot(P, uptake, 'DisplayNone', name, 'LineWidth', 2, 'Color', colors(i,:));
end
xlabel('CO2 Uptake [mmol/g]');
title('Langmuir Isotherm CO2 Uptake for MOFs');

```

Figure 8.2 Shows the MATLAB code used to simulate MOFs performance Isotherm plots

From the figure above MATLAB code was developed using Isotherm-Langmuir model equations was adopted and used to implement the porous packed bed length and diameter alongside the 5 top candidates of MOFs in which comprehensive peer-reviewed from research papers and the cure depict Langmuir isotherm metrics of how the high performance of the metal organic frameworks MOFs Mg-MOF-74 and MIL-101 has the potential of having highest performance in CO2 uptake and adsorption in mol/kg as depicted the plots trends. As shown in table (figure 9.1 to 9.4)

Figure 9.1.a Shows the Langmuir Isotherm plots depicting the metric performance of the top candidate MOFs representation

Figure 9.1.b shows the Langmuir Isotherm plots depicting the metric performance of the top candidate MOFs representation

In the figure below (fig 9.1a, b) depict metric performance of each MOFs in relative to heat loss in kW per CO₂ captured. Figure below (fig 9.2) show temperature contour plots of each metal organic framework MOFs incorporated in MATLAB code to be simulated, and here we can see how the temperature trend was gradually varying along the porous length of packed bed as depicted HKUST-1 has one of the highest temperature concentrations especially toward the boundary of wall probably due to its heat transfer rate and optimum temperature operating value in relation to CO₂ exothermic uptake reaction towards the wall of the packed bed.

Figure 9.2 Shows wall heat temperature contour of the packed bed length representation

Figure 10.1 Plots of Langmuir isotherm CO₂ Uptake of 5 different MOFs

Figure 10.2 Show the metric performance score of CO₂ per kW heat loss uptake per kW heat loss per pressure

Figure 11.1 Plots of CO₂ uptake in mmol/kg versus pressure in bar for Mg-MOF-74 frameworks

Figure 11.3 Plots of CO₂ uptake in mmol/kg versus pressure in bar for ZIF-8 frameworks

Figure 11.5 Plots of CO₂ uptake in mmol/kg versus pressure in bar for HKUST-1 frameworks

Figure 11.7 Plots of CO₂ uptake in mmol/kg versus pressure in bar for UiO-66 frameworks

Figure 11.9 Plots of CO₂ uptake in mmol/kg versus pressure in bar for MIL-101 frameworks

Figure above (fig 11.1 to 11.9) shows the results of the list of high-performance MOFs with wall temperature variation over the pressure impact of CO₂ and uptake.

Figure 12.1 Shows the temperature heat contour plots of all the MOFs selected for the peer review

Result interpretation

Heat generation along the length of the packed bed reactor are depicted above over various high performance MOFs peer reviewed in this project. The extent of temperature rise is correlated with the adsorption capacity and heat of adsorption. MOF-74, MIL-101, AND TAMOF-1 released more heat due to high uptake and stronger adsorbate-adsorbent interaction (fig 12.1). As shown in table (figure 12.1)

Thermal gradients along the length of packed bed were also examined here. Radial heat dispersion is visible from the center to edge, consistent with central adsorption heat zone and peripheral cooling. This is due to the conduction into the cooler bed regions and boundary heat losses.

Adsorption efficiency indicators were also examined here. The higher the temperature in the center, the greater the local adsorption efficiency rate. This makes temperatures contour proxy for real-time adsorption efficiency activity in the bed.

Packed bed design insight was also examined here; the plots are crucial for thermal management. MOFs like MOF-74 may require active cooling systems to avoid hotspots that could degrade the performance or safety of the reactor.

HKUST-1 anomaly was also examined in the result plots, despite the low uptake of CO₂, its relatively sharp temperature contour could be attributed to a higher heat adsorption per mole, possibly due to open metal sites providing stronger binding induced by the exothermic surge (fig 12.1).

Material selection

So therefore, for instance for high-throughput CO₂ capture systems, materials like MOF-74, MIL-101, and TaMOF-1 provide excellent performance but may necessitate more thermal management in materials selection choices

Bed sizing and control

So therefore, for instance moderate performers like PCN-68 and UiO-66 may be thermally more stable, suggesting a trade-off between adsorption efficiency and thermal operability of reactors.

Process safety

So therefore, for instance, the most exothermic MOFs could lead to thermal runaways if not properly cooled, especially in large-scale beds.

Simulation validation

These plots can serve as benchmarks for validating coupled heat-mass transfer models in packed beds reactors.

Conclusion

These heat map arrays visually confirmed the adsorptive and thermal diversity across the eleven MOFs selected from the peer-reviewed literature. These MOFs were selected based on their respective CO₂ uptake targets, thermal stability of the system, desired kinetics as depicted in the K-epsilon ANSYS results, and plots (fig 12.1). These plots offer a powerful metric tool for screening MOFs in the packed-bed CO₂ capture and storage system CCSS, helping optimize performance, safety, and thermal load performance.

MOFs like MOF-74, TaMOF-1, and MIL-101 are high-capacity, highly exothermic, and suitable for fast CO₂ capture systems in characterization, but may require thermal management. Moreover, ZIF-8, BeBTB shows lower uptake of CO₂ and milder thermal behavior, possibly better for temperature-sensitive environments or slow capture systems processes. There are clear indications that thermal gradients can affect long-term structural stability and should be considered in the further analysis of reactor design (fig 12.1).

Limitation

The model tested for simulation here in the project simplifies packed-bed behaviors using the one-dimensional axial flow model, missing the maldistribution seen in the real world industrial adsorbers in CO₂ capture systems mitigating emissions. Also, the model does not account for the CO₂ capture from the flue gas mixture (e.g., CO₂/N₂, CO₂/H₂O) and that the model lacks the thermal or pressure swing regeneration cycles common in United Kingdom capture plants. Also, the model long-term MOFs degradation from cyclic loads, moisture, or temperature is not modelled, as the result may over predict performance, requiring further validation with CFD or pilot-scale rigs.

Project impact

Enable rapid screening of MOFs for CCS using realistic heat, mass and pressure profiles as depicted in the methodology of the project and Matlab code implementation, it also supports early-stage design of CO₂ capture systems for power plant and industrial emitters as the aspect ratio of packed-bed of the porous membrane play a crucial role in designing optimum adsorption of emission, as well as bridge lab-scale MOFs data with engineering-scale packed-bed reactors modelling for deployment. It also supports or reduces the reliance on costly CFD by offering a fast, physics-based simulation tool. It aligns with UK Net Zero goals by accelerating the adoption of efficient MOF-based CCS technologies. Another major impact of this project is about the catalytic converters commonly used in UK to purify emission from the gasoline and diesel engines of post combustion capture used in converting environmentally hazardous exhaust gas emission include carbon dioxide CO₂, carbon monoxide CO, nitrogen oxide NO_x and unburned hydrocarbons fuels CH₄. These exhaust gas emissions are forced through a substrate known as MOFs, which is metal organic frameworks compound with linkers and ligands catalysts in absorbing and separating these emissions, moreover the nature of the these exhaust gas flows play a pivotal role in in determining the performance of the catalytic MOFs packed bed or reactor chamber used in capturing process as well as the importance to the pressure gradient and velocity distribution through the porous bed. The result generated demonstrated the porosity effect of the resistance flow of CO₂ based on how the packed bed MOF was set up.

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Index & Abbreviations

Metal Organic Framework(s),	MOF(s)
Carbon Capture and Storage,	CCS
Carbon Capture and Utilization,	CCU
Packed Bed Reactor,	PBR
Computational Fluid Dynamics,	CFD
Langmuir Isotherm,	LI
Freundlich Isotherm,	FI
Isothermal Adsorption Curve,	IAC
Adsorption-Desorption Cycle,	AD Cycle
Temperature Swing Adsorption,	TSA
Pressure Swing Adsorption,	PSA
Moisture Swing Adsorption,	MSA
Electro-Thermal Swing Adsorption,	ESA
Temperature-Vacuum Swing Adsorption,	TVSA

Scanning Electron Microscopy,	SEM
Transmission Electron Microscopy,	TEM
SolidWorks,	SW
Adsorption Uptake (mmol/g),	Uptake (mmol/g)
Surface Area (cm ² /g),	SA (cm ² /g)
Pore Volume (cm ³ /g),	PV (cm ³ /g)
Pressure (bar),	P (bar)
Temperature (Kelvin),	T (K)
Heat of Adsorption (kJ/mol),	Q _a (kJ/mol)
Langmuir Constant,	K _L
Freundlich Constant,	K _F
Root Mean Square Error,	RMSE
Coefficient of Determination,	R ²
Adsorption Equilibrium Concentration,	C _e
Quantity of Gas Adsorbed,	q _e
Packed Bed Length,	L _{pbr}
Packed Bed Diameter,	D _{pbr}
Number of Data Points,	N _{data}
Computational Domain,	Comp. Domain
Design Modeler (ANSYS Module),	DM
Porous Media Resistance (Viscous/Inertial),	PMR